

Guide to Utilizing Simulation Data for [*Computational Design of Dopant-Free Hole Transporting Materials: Enhancing Stability without Compromising Charge Transport*]: AMBER Inputs, Force Fields, and ADF Calculations

Molecular Dynamics Simulation

The missing parameters for the General Amber Force Field (GAFF) were generated using the Antechamber package. As a result, two output files were produced: X.frcmod and X.prepi (where X represents TQ4, TF1, TF2, and TF4). These files can be used to prepare the initial setup for simulations. The 'X' in all file names corresponds to TQ4, TF1, TF2, and TF4.

The `tleap.in` file (can be used for all systems with slight modifications), which is a script containing several commands, was used to create the initial setup files in Tleap program. You can execute the script using the following command:

➤ `tleap -f tleap.in`

The files required to run a system are available for all systems. To execute a system, the necessary files include the input files (Min, NVT, and NPT), X.prmtop, and X.prmcrd. To run a system that includes water molecules, you only need to execute the job file for each system. The sample JOB_FILE is available and can be used for all systems with slight modification. To execute JOB_AMBER:

On a personal computer, you first need to make the file executable using the `chmod +x` command. For example:

➤ `chmod +x Job_file_name` (example: JOB_AMBER)

After this, you can run the JOB_AMBER file directly.

On a cluster, you can submit the file directly using the `qsub` command. For example:

➤ `qsub Job_file_name`

This will start the simulation.

Refer to the table below for more information about the provided files.

.frcmod	A file containing additional force field parameters for modifying or extending the standard force field for a molecule.
.prepi	A file containing atomic, bonding, and charge information of the molecule, used for system preparation in AMBER simulations.
Input_...	Input file
JOB_AMBER_...	Script for running system
tleap.in	The script containing commands for generating the initial files.
.prmtop	The topology file of the system.
.prmcrd	The coordinates of the atoms in the system.

Calculating Electronic Coupling

There is a folder containing a sample input file for calculating electronic coupling using the ADF package. You can run this file directly in Linux after making it executable with the `chmod` command (as described above).

Finding Missing Parameters for Organic Molecules Using the Antechamber Package in AMBER: A Guide to Building Force Fields

For organic molecules, you can find missing parameters step by step, as described below. First, if you want to use the RESP (restricted electrostatic potential) method, you need to determine the partial charge for each atom. These charges can be obtained using Gaussian 09 software. You should use the following keywords in the Gaussian input file for this purpose:

```
#HF/6-31G* SCF=tight Test Pop=MK iop(6/33=2) iop(6/42=6) opt
```

The `.prepi` file can then be generated directly from the Gaussian output file using the following command:

```
➤ antechamber -fi gout -fo prepi -i output_Gaussian.out -o file_name.prepi  
-c resp -j 5 -at gaff -rn ABC (You can select any three word instead of ABC)
```

antechamber command for using antechamber package

-fi input file format

-fo output file format

-i input file

-o output file

-c charge method

-j atom type and bond type prediction index

-at atom type

-rn residue name

Next, use Parmchk to generate the `.frcmod` file from the `.prepi` file. The `.frcmod` file can be obtained from the `.prepi` file using the following command:

```
➤ parmchk -i file_name.prepi -o file_name.frcmod -f prepi
```

parmchk command for using *parmchk* package

-i input file

-o output file (*.frcmod*)

-f input file format

Now you have both `.frcmod` and `.prepi` file.